

Inert shell effect on the quantum yield of neodymium-doped near-infrared nanoparticles. The necessary shield in an aqueous dispersion.

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ABSTRACT Lanthanide-doped nanoparticles (LnNPs) are versatile near-infrared (NIR) emitting nanoprobes with growing interest for non-invasive biomedicine-related imaging. In the race towards the brightest LnNPs, high photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY) values are attained by implementing core/shell engineering, particularly with an inert shell of carefully selected thickness. In this work, a thorough investigation is performed to quantify how an outer inert shell maintains the PLQY of Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs suspended in an aqueous environment. Three relevant quantitative findings affecting the PLQY of neodymium (Nd³⁺)-doped LnNPs are identified: i) PLQY of core LnNPs is improved 3-fold upon inert shell coating, ii) PLQY decreases with increasing Nd³⁺ doping despite the inert shell, iii) solvent quenching has a major influence on the PLQY of the LnNPs, though it is relatively lessened for high Nd³⁺ doping. Overall, we shed new light on the impact of the LnNP architecture on the NIR emission as well as on the quenching effects caused by doping concentration and solvent molecules.

“Measure what is measurable, and make measurable what is not so” pronounced by Galileo Galilei five hundred years ago still summarizes the key goal of science – quantitative assessment of natural phenomena driven by fundamental exploration and anticipated societal benefits. Having a close look at luminescent nanoparticles for biomedical applications, this is yet a mostly-pending task on many fronts. Widespread claims of high brightness or intense emission frequently lack factual support, as many reports do not present quantitative measurements, like absolute quantum yield. Photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY) is defined as the fraction of emitted photons against the number of absorbed photons.¹ Brightness of a photoluminescent nanoparticle is the product of the PLQY and absorption coefficient of the material.¹ Between absorption and PLQY, the former is an intrinsic characteristic of the material, while PLQY depends on the architecture of the nanoparticle and its immediate environment. The deficit of

quantitative studies referred above is particularly acute for nanoparticles working in the near infrared (NIR) spectral range. Accounting for the photoluminescence in the NIR is becoming ever more relevant to realistically translate nanoparticles to biomedical practices. Within the NIR spectral range, photoluminescent nanoprobe operate deeper within tissues, grant better imaging contrast, and suffer less from background noise, i.e. autofluorescence.^{2,3} As NIR agents, lanthanide-doped nanoparticles (LnNPs) constitute a class of versatile, chemically and optically stable, and (broadly considered) non-toxic nanoprobe to be exploited *in vivo* from imaging to therapy.⁴ Among which, Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs continue to be the preferred “work-horse” for many a such applications. As NIR emitting nanoparticles, in particular, Nd-doped LnNPs have come under intense interest.

It is widely accepted that core/shell engineering of LnNPs allows to substantially improve their PLQY, and subsequently their brightness, by means of an optically inert (undoped) outer shell.⁵ Safeguarding the emission intensity by an inert shell is attained by spatially separating the optically active core from the vibrational modes of the solvent, as well as by the reduction of structural surface defects at the core interface. Notably, recent reports analyzed the coupling between the energy migration (caused by high Ln³⁺ concentration) and surface quenching.^{6,7} This coupling leads to intensity loss by long-scale propagation of the excitation energy towards the energy sinks represented by the surface defects and solvent molecules. Yet in depth studies have been thus far performed only on Er³⁺ and/or Yb³⁺-doped LnNPs.^{6,8} Despite these accepted qualitative notions, very few reports provide quantitative information on the change of absolute PLQY of the NIR emitting LnNPs with inert shell thickness,⁹ Ln³⁺ doping concentration,¹⁰ or the LnNPs' environment.¹¹ The latter two factors are particularly elusive for water dispersed LnNPs operating in the NIR. Many reports concerning the brightness and applicative nature of LnNPs

cannot be compared between each other for lack of quantitative data, and provide no inference about brightness limits of the employed LnNPs due to absence of absolute PLQY measurements. In the category of such less studied NIR probes are aforementioned Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs, which carry a decade worth of biomedical imaging and temperature sensing research,¹²⁻¹⁷ but almost no quantitative data regarding their PLQY in different media. It is worth noting that affordable and reliable PLQY measurements in the NIR became available only recently, which might explain the scarcity of reports on PLQY in the NIR. Hence, it is stimulating and mandatory to fill this knowledge gap with accurate data now, for the well-directed development of NIR emitting LnNPs and their timely translation to the biomedical framework.

In light of this, we characterized the photophysical properties of NaGdF₄:Nd³⁺ core/NaGdF₄ inert shell LnNPs in different media, providing the relevant absolute PLQY values found for a variety of factors that exert influence over the PLQY. The NaGdF₄ host was prioritized for its wide use in developing photoluminescent LnNPs.¹⁸ Among Ln³⁺ ions, Nd³⁺ is intensely employed in NIR imaging as the arrangement of its energy levels favors occurrence of radiative transitions, and its excitation and emission wavelengths lie within the biological imaging windows (BW) – NIR spectral regions best suited for light penetration through tissues.¹⁹

NaGdF₄: x mol% Nd³⁺/NaGdF₄ (x = 5, 12.5 and 25) were synthesized following modified thermal decomposition approach,²⁰ yielding small and monodisperse LnNPs. **Figure 1** shows the transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images of differently doped core-only and core/shell LnNPs, and their respective size distributions. The core-only LnNPs were approximately 11-12 nm in size, while their core/shell analogs had a ~7 nm thick inert shell, increasing the total size of LnNPs to 25-26 nm. The shell width was tailored following the more recent reports on the PLQY vs inert shell thickness demonstrating that 5-10 nm range was considered sufficient to

protect LnNPs from quenching by solvent and capping ligand vibrational modes.^{21,22} All LnNPs crystallized in pure hexagonal phase, confirmed by powder x-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements (Figure S1); and actual Nd³⁺ doping amounts, evaluated by the inductively coupled plasma analysis (ICP), matched intended target values (Table S1). The synthesized oleic acid capped LnNPs were dispersed in hexane, and transferred to water via a ligand removal procedure.²³

Figure 1. TEM images and respective size distributions of core-only (A) and core/shell (B) NaGdF₄: x mol% Nd³⁺/NaGdF₄ LnNPs, where x = 5, 12.5 and 25. Scale bars are 50 nm.

Under 804 nm excitation, all LnNPs exhibited NIR emission bands around 880, 1060 and 1340 nm, which respectively correspond to the ⁴F_{3/2} → ⁴I_{9/2}, ⁴I_{11/2}, and ⁴I_{13/2} radiative transitions of

Nd^{3+} . In **Figure 2** the representative emission spectra of core-only and core/shell Nd^{3+} -doped LnNPs can be seen. The photoluminescence intensity of the LnNPs is quenched for both core-only and core/shell architectures as Nd^{3+} doping is increased from 5 to 25 mol%, due to concentration quenching noted previously.^{24,25} Different doping concentrations do not seem to influence the relative contribution of the individual emission bands to the net spectrum of Nd^{3+} , thus following the host-dependent branching ratios of Nd^{3+} . The most intense transition remains at around 1060 nm (${}^4\text{F}_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{11/2}$), while the transition at 1340 nm (${}^4\text{F}_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{13/2}$) is the weakest. It is worth noting that in contrast to other reports on Nd^{3+} -doped LnNPs, the intensity of the band around 880 nm (${}^4\text{F}_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{9/2}$) is seen to be on par with that of the 1060 nm (${}^4\text{F}_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{11/2}$). This difference might stem from the fact that Nd^{3+} spectra in various LnNPs are commonly acquired with setups not calibrated for the spectral responsivity in the NIR region, leading to the general notion that the emission intensity of the ${}^4\text{F}_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{9/2}$ transition is much lower than that of ${}^4\text{F}_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{11/2}$.^{26,27} Following this initial assessment of the LnNPs, we sought to quantitatively determine their NIR downshifting emission efficiency (in terms of PLQY) and how it is influenced by cross-relaxation and solvent induced quenching (Figure 2B).

Figure 2. Photoluminescence spectra (A) of core-only (left) and core/shell (right) NaGdF₄: x mol% Nd³⁺/NaGdF₄ LnNPs (x = 5, 12.5 and 25) under 804 nm excitation ($^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4F_{5/2}$) when dispersed in hexane. Observed emission bands correspond to the $^4F_{3/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{9/2}$, $^4I_{11/2}$, and $^4I_{13/2}$ radiative transitions of Nd³⁺ (B left), energy exchange among Nd³⁺ ions in the form of cross-relaxation and energy migration to the surface (B center and right, respectively), that lead to photoluminescence intensity quenching are also shown.

Photoluminescence decay measurements of the emissive $^4F_{3/2}$ excited state reaffirmed the concentration dependent quenching in Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs irrespective of their architecture or dispersion medium (Figure S2). The average lifetime of the $^4F_{3/2}$ excited state decreased with increasing amount of Nd³⁺ doping, supporting cross-relaxation facilitated non-radiative deactivation of this metastable energy level (**Figure 3A**). Furthermore, average lifetime values increased significantly once the inert NaGdF₄ shell was grown over the Nd³⁺-doped LnNP cores

(Table 1), indicative of suppressed surface related quenching. Yet, the relevance of the inert shell was diminished for highly Nd³⁺-doped samples. Despite the coupling between energy migration (driven by increased Ln³⁺ concentration) and surface quenching, for high Nd³⁺ concentrations the cross-relaxation among these ions becomes an important contributor to the emission intensity loss, together with non-radiative decay to the solvent vibrational modes. Furthermore, only minor decrease in average lifetime values was observed upon transferring Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs from hexane to higher vibrational energies exhibiting solvent such as water. The notorious OH stretching mode (~3400 cm⁻¹) of water acts as an “energy sink” for RE³⁺ excited states deactivating them non-radiatively. Yet, the seemingly unaltered photoluminescence lifetime of Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs gives an impression that water has little effect over the ⁴F_{3/2} emissive state of Nd³⁺.

The PLQY of Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs was systematically investigated following 804 nm laser excitation in the 102-532 W/cm² power density range, employing different reference samples for the PLQY calculation. Although the photoluminescence of Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs stems from single photon absorption-emission processes, known as downshifting (intensity of which has a linear dependence with excitation power density), we sought to confirm that the PLQY of the LnNPs remained stable within the measured excitation power density range and was not altered by side-effects like laser induced heating.^{28,29} Three reference samples were used to calculate PLQY: an empty quartz cuvette, a cuvette filled with hexane or water, and a cuvette with blank LnNPs dispersed in hexane or water. Blank LnNPs were synthesized to represent undoped core-only and core/shell NaGdF₄ LnNPs (Figure S3, S4), in order to account for excitation beam attenuation due to light scattering by the LnNPs themselves.³⁰ The net PLQY of all Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs was independent of the excitation power density (Figure S5, S6). Although some variability occurred

due to low absorbance of the excitation beam and poorer colloidal stability of 5 mol% Nd³⁺-doped core-only and core/shell LnNPs in hexane, and it can be regarded as random distribution of experimental points rather than a distinctive trend.

Across all samples, the estimation of PLQY was particularly sensitive to the reference employed, (Figure S7). When absorbance of photoluminescent sample is low, in the case of low Ln³⁺ doping or concentration of LnNPs in dispersion, it becomes paramount to account for laser beam attenuation due to absorption by the dispersion medium and light scattering by the nanoparticles. Pure dispersion media and blank LnNPs as a reference allowed to measure PLQY values more accurately, otherwise underestimated when using an empty cuvette as a reference. This was particularly true in the case of 5 mol% Nd³⁺ doping, where excitation light absorption was overestimating by net contribution from LnNPs and the dispersant. Given the above observations, further PLQY analysis was carried out on values obtained with blank LnNPs as a reference and averaging PLQY values across all excitation power densities. The PLQY of individual NIR emission bands of Nd³⁺ revealed nearly even contribution of 800 (⁴F_{3/2} → ⁴I_{9/2}) and 1060 nm (⁴F_{3/2} → ⁴I_{11/2}) emission to the net PLQY of Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs, irrespective of their architecture or dispersion media (Figure S8). However relative contribution of NIR emission around 1340 nm (⁴F_{3/2} → ⁴I_{13/2}) to the net PLQY decreased from about 8-9% to 2-3% when LnNPs were transferred from hexane to water. This can be attributed to the partial overlap between the absorption band of water around 1430 nm and 1340 nm emission band of Nd³⁺, masking true contribution of ⁴F_{3/2} → ⁴I_{13/2} radiative transition to the net PLQY.

Figure 3. Average lifetime τ (A) and total PLQY (B) of NaGdF₄: x mol% Nd³⁺/NaGdF₄ LnNPs (x = 5, 12.5 and 25) under 804 nm excitation when dispersed in hexane (red data points) or water (blue) in their core-only or core/shell formulations. Lines are guides to the eye. Schematic representation (C) of the opposite effects on the PLQY of LnNPs: improvement with the addition of an inert shell, and decrease when LnNPs are dispersed in a solvent of high quenching strength such as water. Relative brightness (D), as a figure of merit comparison between the Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs of different architectures and dispersed in a different media.

The net PLQY of core-only and core/shell Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs in two different media and at varying Nd³⁺ doping concentration is shown in Figure 3B and is summarized in Table 1. The highest PLQY was measured for core/shell 5 mol% Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs dispersed in hexane, $17.4 \pm 2.5\%$, while the PLQY of the same particles dispersed in water was $8.8 \pm 0.9\%$. In contrast, the lowest PLQY was exhibited by core-only 25 mol% Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs, $1.1 \pm 0.1\%$ in hexane and $0.5 \pm 0.1\%$ in water. On average the PLQY of Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs was improved moving from core-only to core/shell architecture by 2.5 and 3.4 times for hexane and water dispersions, respectively, attesting to greater photoluminescence intensity quenching by water. Two key

aspects can be drawn from these observations: i) PLQY of Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs decreases with both doping amount and transfer from hexane to water, yet ii) partial safeguarding of emission intensity can be obtained employing inert shell coating (Figure 3C).

A closer look at the average lifetime and PLQY data of Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs revealed a few peculiarities specific to Nd³⁺ ions. In line with average lifetime data, net PLQY decreased at increasing Nd³⁺ doping, irrespective of the inert shell coating, confirming our inference about cross-relaxation playing a detrimental role in quenching emission intensity of Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs. Furthermore, for the completely unprotected core-only LnNPs, transfer from hexane to water curbed the PLQY by 50-60%, with slight dependence on the Nd³⁺ concentration. Yet the same decrease (~55%) in core/shell LnNPs was observed only for the 5 mol% Nd³⁺ doping, other samples having 17 and 26% decrease in PLQY for 12.5 and 25 mol% Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs, respectively. This again indicated that quenching by water is less relevant in highly Nd³⁺-doped samples, concentration quenching being the predominant mechanism. As noted previously, the photoluminescence decay measurements showed only marginal change when moving from hexane to water dispersions, particularly in the case of core/shell Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs – only up to 6% decrease was observed for the average lifetime of the ⁴F_{3/2} excited state. Given these observations, we speculated that photoluminescence decay measurements account only for the quenching of the ⁴F_{3/2} emitting state of Nd³⁺, whereas decreased PLQY can be associated with direct quenching of the light absorbing ⁴F_{5/2} state. Our assumption relied on the fact that quenching by the OH stretching mode around 3400 cm⁻¹ is in close resonance with the ⁴F_{5/2}-⁴I_{15/2} energy gap (Figure S9A), but would require additional release or absorption of multiple lattice phonons to bridge the ⁴F_{3/2}-⁴I_{15/2} or ⁴F_{3/2}-⁴I_{13/2} energy gap, respectively. To test our hypothesis, we have measured the lifetime of ⁴F_{5/2} excited state for 5 mol % Nd³⁺-doped RENPs in their

core-only or core/shell formulation, when dispersed in hexane or water (Figure S9B). However, similar excited state lifetime trends to $^4F_{3/2}$ energy level were observed for the $^4F_{5/2}$ one, thus disproving our hypothesis. Another aspect worth considering is the water absorption, which increases between 1050 nm and 1400 nm (from ca. 0.06 to 1 cm^{-1}). The experimental configuration for the PLQY measurements makes the photon, once emitted from Nd^{3+} , to reflect of the integrating sphere walls multiple times and have many passes through the cuvette filled with water. This increases the likelihood of photons being lost to water absorption and artificially lower measured PLQY, rather than stemming from an intrinsic excited state quenching by solvent vibrational modes. At this point, we leave this open to discussion, as it merits further more focused analysis on the possible external and internal factors that could affect the PLQY of Nd^{3+} -doped RENPs, but are outside the scope of the present work.

Table 1. Comparison of average lifetimes values, τ , and PLQY of core-only and core/shell NaGdF_4 : x mol% $\text{Nd}^{3+}/\text{NaGdF}_4$ LnNPs (x = 5, 12.5 and 25) dispersed in hexane and water.

	Average lifetime τ , μs				PLQY, %			
	core-only		core/shell		core-only		core/shell	
	hexane	water	hexane	water	hexane	water	hexane	water
Nd^{3+} , mol%								
5	44.9	36.5	135.8	130.2	8.2 \pm 0.9	3.1 \pm 0.3	17.4 \pm 2.5	8.8 \pm 0.9
12.5	14.5	12.3	34.3	33.5	2.5 \pm 0.2	1.1 \pm 0.1	5.4 \pm 0.5	4.4 \pm 0.4
25	6.5	4.0	12.2	11.5	1.1 \pm 0.1	0.5 \pm 0.1	2.7 \pm 0.3	1.9 \pm 0.2

Focusing on the data for 5 mol% Nd^{3+} -doped LnNPs (Table 1) allows us to empirically distinguish the different contribution of the solvent and surface effects, leaving aside the influence of concentration quenching. For the core-only LnNPs, the effect of coupling to water vibrations is reflected in a 60% reduction of the PLQY value referenced to that measured in hexane (from 8.2 \pm 0.9 to 3.1 \pm 0.3%). This decrease is arguably attributable to the quenching by

solvent with higher frequency vibrational modes. We can state that because the LnNPs are the same (composition- and morphology-wise) for both measured values, quenching by surface defects was already accounted for within the PLQY measured in hexane. Provided with this semi-empirical asset, now we extend the comparison to the core/shell 5 mol% Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs, observing an almost 3-fold increase by adding the outer inert shell. However, for a core-only to core/shell comparison, both LnNPs dispersed in water, it is not possible to assign unequivocally such PLQY increase to a complete screening of optically active ions from the vibrational modes of water molecules by the inert shell. Indeed, it is only possible to add together both factors, i.e. that aforementioned screening from vibrational quenching and removal of surface defects, synergistically contribute to a PLQY improvement from 3.1±0.3% to 8.8±0.9%, ultimately caused by adding the outer inert shell.

It is worth noting that comparison of our measured values with previous reports, however, remains tricky, as other studies used different measurement methods, particles of different sizes, compositions, or dispersed in different media, while some of these parameters were not reported altogether (Table S2). This further highlights the necessity for a systematic absolute PLQY analysis of NIR emitting LnNPs developed for biomedical use.

Finally, to illustrate the brightness of all LnNPs we compared it in relative terms considering the product of PLQY and the number of absorbing Nd³⁺ ions per LnNPs (Figure 3D, also see SI). As expected, the brightest Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs were those featuring an inert shell, and hexane dispersions were brighter than water. Nonetheless, it can be seen that although absolute PLQY decreases significantly as a function of Nd³⁺ doping amount, the relative brightness of these LnNPs is less affected, particularly in the case of core/shell Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs in water. Reduced PLQY of Nd³⁺-doped LnNPs can be partially compensated by increased absorbance

due to the higher number of Nd^{3+} . Yet, LnNPs with low Nd^{3+} doping are in general brighter, settling the dispute among some contradictory reports on the optimal Nd^{3+} doping concentration in LnNPs.³¹⁻³⁴ Furthermore, LnNPs with low Nd^{3+} doping should be preferred in imaging and nanothermometry applications, as higher Nd^{3+} content can lead to undesired heating or unreliable temperature measurements due to the self-absorption induced artifacts.^{35,36}

In summary, we have prepared a library of Nd^{3+} -doped NaGdF_4 LnNPs and thoroughly examined their photophysical characteristics. The main emphasis was given to absolute PLQY values, as a function of Nd^{3+} doping, core/shell engineering, and colloidal dispersion media. Our findings matched previous studies regarding the inert shelling protection of photoluminescence intensity of LnNPs. Yet, we observed the non-negligible phenomenon of concentration quenching playing a significant role in Nd^{3+} -doped LnNPs, reducing PLQY as Nd^{3+} concentration increases in an inversely proportional manner (double the Nd^{3+} content translates into halving PLQY). Core/shell 5 mol% Nd^{3+} -doped LnNPs were the brightest overall, and thus should be preferred in biomedical imaging and nanothermometry applications. Furthermore, we emphasize the importance of reference sample selection in determining the PLQY as excitation beam attenuation by the dispersion media absorption and scattering of the LnNPs can lead to underestimation of the PLQY. We believe that this report will help to rationally design advanced multilayered structures of Nd^{3+} -doped NPs and facilitate their real-life use as deep-tissue NIR probes.

METHODS

More detailed information regarding the LnNP synthesis, surface treatment, structural and spectroscopic characterization is provided in the Supporting Information.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Complete LnNP synthesis and characterization description. Additional XRD, ICP-OES, photoluminescence decay and PLQY data; including Figures S1-S9 and Table S1 (PDF).

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Author Contributions

A. B. and A. S. conceived the project. A. S. synthesized and characterized the LnNPs, conducted the spectroscopic measurements, measured the PLQY of LnNPs dispersed in hexane, and performed data analysis. C.B. measured the PLQY of LnNPs dispersed in water. I. R. M. and A.B performed photoluminescence decay measurements. The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript. †These authors contributed equally.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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